

Kinetics of the Acid-mediated Dissociation of Mixed Chelate Complexes : Aquation of Bis(acetylacetonato)ethylenediamine and Acetylacetonatobis(ethylenediamine)cobalt(III) Complexes

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Mechanisms of the acid-mediated dissociation of two mixed chelate complexes, bis(acetylacetonato)ethylenediamine and acetylacetonatobis(ethylenediamine)cobalt(III) ions have been investigated spectrophotometrically. In the presence of perchloric acid the first complex dissociates to cobaltous ion, free ethylenediamine, free acetylacetonone and oxidised products of acetylacetonone. The dissociation follows an acid-assisted path. Rate constant (k_{obs}) for the complexes have been evaluated. A mechanism has been proposed for the first complex.

Numerous studies on the kinetics of acid-catalysed dissociation of chelate complexes of cobalt(III) are available in the literature¹⁻⁵. For flexible basic bidentate ligands, protonation of the bound ligand leads to its dissociation⁶. In mixed chelate complex, however, a competition for protonation by the ligands may control the overall mechanism. There are a few scattered studies on such reactions, mostly with multidentate amines and oxalato⁷⁻¹⁰ or carbonato ligands. Trisethylenediaminecobalt(III) complex ion does not possess any basic site which may interact with H⁺ ion to lead a catalysed reaction. Replacement of one ethylenediamine by aqua or ammonia molecules does not change the reactivity pattern of the complex ion for the same reason^{12,13}. Numerous mechanistic studies on the reaction of tris- β -diketonato complexes of metal ions are available in literature^{2,14,15,16}. Acid-catalysed dissociation of trisacetylacetonatochromium(III) and trisacetylacetonato-cobalt(III) complexes proceeds by the protonation of one of the bound ligands, leading to its rupture from the metal centre. The chromium(III) complex dissociates successively to bis- and monoacetylacetonato complexes and finally forms hexaaqua complex ion. On the other hand, the cobalt(III) complex gives oxidation products of acetylacetonone along with free acetylacetonone, and a lower oxidation state (Co²⁺) for the metal ion^{15,16}. The present investigation was undertaken to study systematically the acid-mediated dissociation of mixed chelate complexes of cobalt(III) containing ethylenediamine and acetylacetonato ligands. The mixed chelates chosen are bis(acetylacetonato)ethylenediaminecobalt(III) and acetylacetonatobis(ethylenediamine)cobalt(III) ions.

Results and Discussion

Good first order rate plots for the bis(acetylacetonato)ethylenediamine complex were obtained at all concentrations of acid (always in excess) and temperatures. Table 1 records the k_{obs} values thus obtained at different acid con-

centrations and temperatures. Plots of k_{obs} versus acid concentration at all the temperatures are linear with positive slopes but no intercepts on the rate axis (figure not shown). This leads to a rate equation of the form,

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Rate} &= k_2 [\text{H}^+][\text{Complex}] \\ &= k_{obs} [\text{Complex}] \end{aligned}$$

Therefore, $k_{obs} = k_2 [\text{H}^+]$ (1)

where, k_2 is a second order rate constant. It is also observed that the rate of reaction does not vary with change in dielectric constant of the medium.

TABLE 1 - RATE CONSTANTS AND ACTIVATION PARAMETERS FOR THE ACID-MEDIATED DISSOCIATION OF [Co(acac)₂(en)]ClO₄

[Complex] = 1 × 10 ⁻³ mol dm ⁻³ , I = 3.0 mol dm ⁻³ (NaClO ₄)	10 ⁶ k _{obs} (s ⁻¹)		
[HClO ₄] mol dm ⁻³	73°	78°	88°
0.5	2.5	4.05	9.2
0.8	4.09	5.9	14.5
1.0	4.9	7.5	17.87
1.2	5.5	8.89	21.45
1.5	7.2	11.2	26.89
2.0	8.9	15.3	35.55
2.5	11.05	18.2	44.9
2nd-order rate constant	4.5 ± 0.1	7.5 ± 0.1	18.0 ± 0.2
10 ⁶ k ₁ (mol ⁻¹ s ⁻¹)			
ΔH [‡] (kJ mol ⁻¹)	92 ± 8		
ΔS [‡] (JK ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹)	-74 ± 12		

The enthalpy and entropy of activation for the system were evaluated using the Eyring equation (ΔH[‡] = 92 ± 8 kJ mol⁻¹ and ΔS[‡] = -74 ± 12 JK⁻¹ mol⁻¹). These values are comparable to those of acid decomposition of Cr(acac)₃, Ru(bzac)₃ and Ru(acac)₃ (Table 2). A moderately positive

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enthalpy value is to be expected due to bond-breaking between acetylacetonate and the metal centre (endoergic), simultaneously with a bond-formation with water molecule (exoergic). The moderately negative entropy of activation is also explained on a similar agreement.

TABLE 2—ACTIVATION PARAMETERS OF METAL-β-DIKETONATE COMPLEXES

Compd.	[H ⁺] dep. path		[H ⁺] ² dep. path		Ref.
	ΔH [‡]	ΔS [‡]	ΔH [‡]	ΔS [‡]	
	kJ mol ⁻¹	JK ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹	kJ mol ⁻¹	JK ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹	
[Co(acac) ₂ (en)] ⁺	92 ±8	-74 ±12	-	-	Present work
[Cr(acac) ₃]	84.5	-59.4	-	-	15
[Ru(bzac) ₃]	69 ±5	-107 ±10	-	-	21
[Ru(acac) ₃]	86.5 ±7	-52.3 ±10	67 ±5	-92 ±8	21
[Co(acac) ₃]	138	102	-	-	2

In case of [Cr(acac)₃], [Ru(acac)₃] and [Ru(bzac)₃] complexes, it has been suggested that protonation of the bound ligand at the carbonyl oxygen can facilitate the chelate ring opening leading to loss of its quasi-aromatic character. The same may hold good in the present case as well. Consistent with all these observations, a mechanism has been proposed as given in Scheme 1.

Scheme 1

Application of steady state approximation to intermediate [B] gives the rate expression as

$$\text{Rate} = \frac{k_2 k_1}{k_{-2} + k_1} [\text{Co(en)(acac)}_2^+][\text{H}^+]$$

It may be reasonably assumed that $k_{-2} > k_1$,

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Therefore, Rate} &= (k_2/k_{-2}) k_1 [\text{Complex}][\text{H}^+] \\ &= k_{\text{obs}} [\text{Complex}] \end{aligned}$$

$$\text{where, } k_{\text{obs}} = (k_2/k_{-2}) k_1 [\text{H}^+]$$

An attempt was made at this stage to follow the kinetics of the acetylacetonatobis(ethylenediamine) complex at 90° in the presence of 1.0 mol dm⁻³ perchloric acid. The absorbance of the complex changes very slowly with time and

because of the limitation of the measuring device, the rate constant has been obtained with, rather, a higher uncertainty. The value of k_{obs} obtained in this case is $(7.4 \pm 5.0) \times 10^{-9} \text{ s}^{-1}$. These observations show that the replacement of acetylacetonate chelate by ethylenediamine contributes to higher stability of the complex. Rate constants of these complexes along with the trisacetylacetonate and trisethylenediamine complexes in presence of 2.0 mol dm⁻³ (HClO₄) at 55° are given in Table 3.

TABLE 3—RATE CONSTANTS OF SOME Co^{III} COMPLEXES AT 2.0 mol dm⁻³ HClO₄ AND AT 55°

Compd.	10 ⁵ k_{obs} (s ⁻¹)	Ref.
[Co(acac) ₃]	29.4	2
[Co(acac) ₂ (en)] ⁺	0.183	Present work
[Co(acac)(en)] ²⁺	0.00074	Present work
	(at 90°, 1.0 mol dm ⁻³ HClO ₄)	
[Co(en) ₃] ³⁺	0.0	Ref. 1

So the complexes may be arranged according to their kinetic lability in the following order : [Co(acac)₃] > [Co(acac)₂(en)]⁺ > [Co(acac)(en)]²⁺ > [Co(en)₃]³⁺. The inertness of the monoacetylacetonato complex is in agreement with some other complexes and seems to be due to its increased thermodynamic stability. In this respect it resembles the trisethylenediamine complex more than the others.

Experimental

Bis(acetylacetonato)ethylenediaminecobalt(III) perchlorate was prepared by the reported method¹⁷ (Found : Co, 13.9; C, 34.22; H, 5.02; N, 6.56. [Co(acac)₂(en)](ClO₄) requires : Co, 14.16; C, 34.6; H, 5.28; N, 6.73%). Acetylacetonatobis(ethylenediamine)cobalt(III) perchlorate complex was prepared by the reported method¹⁸ (Found : Co, 12.22; C, 22.2; N, 11.55. [Co(acac)(en)₂](ClO₄)₂ requires : Co, 12.4; C, 22.6; N, 11.7%).

All reagents used were of reagent grade else purified by suitable methods. Distilled water redistilled in an all-glass apparatus was used for making the solutions. The rate constants for the acid-mediated dissociation of the complexes were followed spectrophotometrically with a SICO 110D spectrophotometer. Spectra of a series of solutions of each of these complexes ($1 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$) containing different amounts of acid (HClO₄) varying from 0.5 to 2.5 mol dm⁻³, were recorded immediately after preparation and after 2, 4, 6.....h, 1, 2, 3, ...days upto two weeks at room temperature. The bis-acac complex showed good spectral change but the mono-acac complex showed a small change even at 90°. Kinetic runs were carried out at the λ_{max} of the complexes (540 and 500 nm for the bis- and the mono-acac complexes respectively). Aliquots (3 ml) of the reacting solutions were withdrawn at required intervals, quenched in ice-cooled water around 5° and absorbances measured. The pseudo-first order rate constants for each stage were evaluated graphically by plotting $\log(A_0 - A_\infty)/(A_t - A_\infty)$

versus time. The concentration changes of the complexes if any in the measurement of the rate constants at different temperatures had been ignored. As the reactivity of the mono-acac complex was very small no worthwhile rate measurements could be made with this complex. The reactions were studied at higher $[H^+]$ to have reasonable spectral changes, as at low $[H^+]$ spectral changes observed were very low.

Identification of products and stoichiometry of the reaction : The final spectrum of the solution of $[Co(en)(acac)_2]ClO_4$ (0.001 mol) in 2 M $HClO_4$ at 75° after the period of 7 days, was identical to that of $Co(ClO_4)_2$ (0.001 mol) in 2 M $HClO_4$, which established Co^{II} being the final product of the redox reaction. After completion of the reaction, the mixture was partially evaporated, neutralised with potassium bicarbonate, cooled and then H_2S gas was passed to remove the Co^{II} as CoS . After filtration, the dissolved H_2S gas was removed, treated with a slight excess of copper(II) acetate solution, and then extracted with chloroform to remove all the acetylacetonate as $Cu(acac)_2$ ¹⁹ which indicated that free acetylacetonate was a reaction product.

In order to ascertain the stoichiometry of the reaction, the total concentration of free acetylacetonate in the reaction mixture was estimated spectrophotometrically with *o*-phenylenediamine in acidic medium²⁰. The result indicated that the product solution contained about 1 mole of free acetylacetonate per mole of the original complex, the remaining acetylacetonate molecule having been destroyed (oxidised) in the reaction simultaneously with the reduction of all the Co^{III} to Co^{II} . According to a previous report² the oxidation products of acetylacetonate radical produced are acetone, water and oxygen.

The formation of free radical was confirmed by treating a solution of the complex (1×10^{-3} mol dm^{-3}) in $HClO_4$ (2 mol dm^{-3}) with methyl methacrylate (1 ml), and the mixture was flushed with pure nitrogen and maintained at room temperature for 2–3 days. The appearance of white turbidity indicated that the reaction proceeded by a free radical mechanism.

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